

ENSURING THE RIGHTS OF THE CHILD IN SOCIETY

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7685897>

ELSEVIER

Foundation of Advanced Research & Education's

Received: 22-02-2023

Accepted: 22-02-2023

Published: 22-02-2023

Sultanova Nazakatkhon Atabek daughter

Fergana State University
Student of the direction of social work

Abstract:
Keywords:

About: FARS Publishers has been established with the aim of spreading quality scientific information to the research community throughout the universe. Open Access process eliminates the barriers associated with the older publication models, thus matching up with the rapidity of the twenty-first century.

The role of the family and the educational environment in it is great in the fact that a person comes into the world and matures. The correct formation of relations between parental children in the household affects not only the peace of the family, but also the well-being of society.

Today, no case can justify parental violence against children.

Violence threatens not only the physical health of children, but also the emotional well-being and future of children. Negative consequences can be irreversible if the child has experienced or witnessed violence at an early age, at an important stage in the development of the body and brain. Violence affects the physical and mental health of children, reduces their ability to receive education and socialize, prevents them from becoming psychologically healthy adults and forming good parents.

Unfortunately, child abuse in the family remains a social norm. Often its consequences are not discussed. There are parents who believe that violence is necessary to raise a child, physical strength can be used as punishment. A child who, according to our ancient tradition, is considered an angel to a child, has always been considered innocent, today's society, the difficulties and or opportunities in life make children grow up quickly. A society that first raises a person from the head as a person of innocence, later as a bad person, there must be vices in it in fact. The child looks like white paper, what we teach them will return. It means that before educating a child, we must reform ourselves, society. Abdullah Avlani said the same truth when he said, "upbringing is for us either life - or death, or salvation - or destruction, or happiness - or a matter of disaster,²⁰⁷ " it is for this

²⁰⁷ Abdulla Avlani..Turkish Gulistan or ethics-Tashkent: youth publishing house, 2019. - Page 6

reason that it is necessary to ensure the family environment of children, the spiritual perfection of parents. After all, the bird does what it sees in the nest.

The severity of parents' living conditions, poverty and poverty, their alcohol consumption and abandonment of their children and their migration increase the risk of child neglect, humiliation or exploitation. Children practically do not talk about cases of violence at all, and therefore rarely receive the necessary support from the side of society. In our country, the "Convention on the rights of the child" was ratified on December 9, 1992. Our state undertakes to protect all the rights of children recorded in this international document, including physical, mental and sexual violence, torture or treatment in other forms of cruelty, gross or degrading human dignity.

The law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "on guarantees of the rights of the Child" defines as one of the main directions of the state policy on the protection of the rights of the child to protect the life and health of the child, prevent discrimination of the child, protect the honor and dignity of the child, ensure equality of the rights and (Article 4)²⁰⁸

At the same time, in this law, the state must take the necessary measures to ensure that the child is protected from discrimination of all forms, each child has the right to protection from encroachment on his honor and dignity, from unlawful interference in his personal life, the state from physical, mental and sexual violence, torture or cruel, rude or it is established that a person carries out protection against the treatment of other forms of degrading dignity. (Article 7)²⁰⁹

There are three main types of child abuse, which are:

1. Physical violence,
2. Sexual abuse,
3. Mental abuse.

Physical abuse can occur between children of both sexes, but it is often common among boys children by causing physical damage from themselves to adults through which their psyche is broken. Children and girls of adolescent age meet for sexual abuse. If the children who have fallen into this state are not mentally supported, in the future they will remain a mail to the suisit, such children should be given atrogynous explanations on the mountain of the holiness of life.

Mental abuse is considered the most common type of violence when children are not given enough attention from their parents, not counting on their interests, not respecting their decisions lead to mental disorders in children.

Children grow up with deviant behavior if the later stages of violence are not sufficiently rehabilitated. Deviant behavior-deviant behavior (deviant, lat. deviatio-

²⁰⁸ Convention on the rights of the child. Article 4. www.tergov.uz.

²⁰⁹ Article 7 of the convention on the rights of the child. www.tergov.uz.

deviation) is said to morality, in which the type of actions, activities of a person are different from the usual, generally accepted norms, or are manifested in their deviation from their social norms in a stable manner, not corresponding to the norms adopted by the society in which he is a member. Deviant behavior is often an attempt to leave Society, avoid the problems and difficulties of everyday life, overcome the state of uncertainty and tension through certain forms of compensation. Sexual deviations, alcoholism, drug addiction, etc. are associated with personal disorder, in other words, mental deviations. The main forms of Deviant behavior include delinquency, including crime, drunkenness, drug addiction, prostitution, and suicide. There is an inextricable link between the development of deviant behavior among the younger generation, reaching maturity, and the growth of crime phenomena in society day by day. The desire to commit illegal actions is increasing with the development of deviant behavior of children and adolescents. The main reason for the formation of Deviant behavior is the intensification of Zamo, the inability to accept economic inequality, mass globalization, free access to information, migration, child expropriation, the development of democracy, as well as social phenomena often cause negative reactions in the adolescent environment. Deviant behavior depends on social, biological and psychological factors that must be taken into account when educating young people. In a society with a whole head in general in children, the deviation in the minds of children is a big problem, focusing on these problems, we feel that the crises that occur in different periods of children's life become important in their subsequent life, in finding enough place in society. It is during these crises that children will be able to find their place in life in the future if they receive enough attention and enough affection. Eric Erickson, creator of ego - personality theory, identified 8 stages of psychosocial personality development. As a result of changes in the age of the child in these 8 Stages, various psychosocial disorders arise in him. At the third stage of psychosocial development (3-6 years), a psychological crisis is accompanied by the formation of feelings of guilt, self-denial and futility, which can subsequently lead to addiction, giftedness or fraud, personality disorders.²¹⁰ Also B.M. Miller notes that for a preschool child, the concept of "death" is determined by the loss of the mother, and this often causes their unconscious fears and worries. The fear of parental death in mentally healthy preschool children was observed in 53% of boys and 61% of girls. Fear of one's own death was recorded in 47 percent of boys and 70 percent of girls. Suicide cases are rare in children under 5 years of age, but there has been a tendency for them to grow in the last decade. Today there are women who have experienced family violence families in the families of children who have grown up, the developmental coefficient of

²¹⁰ Book "childhood and society" (Eric Erickson, 1963)

children with deviant behavior is slightly higher. The main reason for this is the end of life for children as described above death is measured by the death of the mother, the compression of the mother by the regular father, in the child who sees harassment being carried out, there are cases of hatred for the father, of dissatisfaction with his life in addition, they live in fear of losing

Children with Deviant behavior seek to expel the bad energies they receive from the environment in others, trying to break the will of weak individuals in the team, trying to humiliate them and enjoy them, as a result of which they become bullies. From this, an ideological emptiness appears in the minds of children, they want to fill such gaps in the path of their goal so that as a result they can become terrorists, drug addicts first president of the Republic of Uzbekistan I.A.Karimov"... it is necessary to prevent the emergence of a vacuum - gap both in politics and in social life and in science. That is, if you do not have your own idea, a foreign idea will come and Reign In Your Land. Such ideological gaps should first be removed from the family environment. The flow of Thieves, offenders is developing in society due to material shortages in the family or as a result of an increase in needs, a light outlook on life.²¹¹

Due to the fact that parents are far from their children to work or leave for another country for certain reasons, children need affection, grow up with a sense of unnecessary, so the flow of prostitutes in society is increasing. To eliminate these vices, it is necessary to reform the media first. Cartoons and motion pictures broadcast on TV channels should be broadcast, seeing that they correspond to the age level of children. It is necessary to strengthen the cooperation of a social worker, a psychologist with primary school students of schools. In addition, parents should pay attention to the fact that children are spending many hours a day. When our holy religion says in Islam "a parent cannot give his child anything better than beautiful upbringing, decency", it is implied that parents teach the child first of all good manners, which is important in the life of the child. To establish an economic life today, parents did not devote time to their children. Children who have grown up in such conditions do not understand enough of their parenting task in the future.

Our President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev spoke about children at a meeting with teachers on December 29," today we also need to increase the responsibility of parents. We will not achieve anything until we change the attitude of parents to education,"²¹² he said.

Children are not born bad them Society vices in it, violence leaves its inexhaustible wound in the lives of children, so that as a result, children react to

²¹¹On the way to spiritual elevation. I.A.Karimov. Tashkent Publishing House "Uzbekistan". 1998.442-page.

²¹² From the president's speech with teachers on 29.12.2022.

society through bad habits .So in recent years, various state circles, sports classes have been organized to spend children's free time meaningfully. Within the framework of the five initiatives, blind contests with various incentives are being held. Only children who have sufficiently distributed their time will have their own views, instead of their own in society. A society without young people who cannot think independently will be exposed in the future. After all, attention to children is attention to the future.

USED LITERATURE:

1. Abdulla Avlani..Turkish Gulistan or ethics-Tashkent: youth publishing house, 2019. - 96 6. Page 6
2. Convention on the rights of the child. Article 4. www.tergov.uz.
3. Book "childhood and society" (Eric Erickson, 1963)
4. Article 7 of the convention on the rights of the child. www.tergov.uz.
5. A.I. Zakharov, 1988.
6. On the way to spiritual elevation. I.A.Karimov. Tashkent Publishing House "Uzbekistan". 1998.442-page.
7. Parental and Child Rights in Islam. (Imam Termiziy narration)
8. From the president's speech with teachers on 29.12.2022.
9. From the President's speech with teachers on 29.12.2022.
10. www.cyberleninka.uz